

Hollow Beam Optical Ponderomotive Trap for Ultracold Neutral Plasma – Dataset

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December 15, 2025

Version v2.0

Abstract

This dataset contains the numerical data and all information required to reproduce the results reported in the manuscript.

1 Hardware and LAMMPS

LAMMPS was compiled and run using the Spack package manager with AMD Optimizing C/C++ and Fortran Compilers (AOCC) following the guidelines on the official AMD web site.

The computations were performed on two machines with 16- and 64-core AMD CPUs. Both machines run Manjaro Linux. Information about the operating system, CPU model, LAMMPS version, and installed packages is given below.

1.1 First Machine: 64 cores (128 threads)

1.1.1 About OS and CPU

```
$ neofetch --stdout

OS: Manjaro Linux x86_64
Kernel: 6.5.13-7-MANJARO
Packages: 1428 (pacman)
Shell: bash 5.2.32
CPU: AMD EPYC 7742 (128) @ 2.250GHz
GPU: 82:00.0 ASPEED Technology, Inc.
      ASPEED Graphics Family
Memory: 13616MiB / 64136MiB
```

1.1.2 About LAMMPS

```
$ spack -V

0.22.0.dev0 (2bcfb72d38daa2d148b5551c21a424633339649c)

$ spack load lammmps@20231121
$ lmp -h

Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel
Simulator - 21 Nov 2023

<...>

Compiler: Clang C++ AMD Clang 16.0.3 (CLANG:
AOCC_4.1.0-Build#270 2023_07_10) with OpenMP 5.0
C++ standard: C++11
MPI v3.1: Open MPI v5.0.1, package: Open MPI
epyc@epyc-server Distribution, ident: 5.0.1,
repo rev: v5.0.1, Dec 20, 2023

Accelerator configuration:

OPENMP package API: OpenMP
OPENMP package precision: double
INTEL package API: OpenMP
INTEL package precision: single mixed double

Active compile time flags:

-DLAMMPS_GZIP
-DFFT_SINGLE
-DLAMMPS_SMALLBIG
sizeof(smallint): 32-bit
sizeof(imageint): 32-bit
sizeof(tagint): 32-bit
sizeof(bigint): 64-bit

<...>

Installed packages:

FEP INTEL KSPACE LEPTON MANYBODY MOLECULE
OPENMP OPT RIGID
```

<...>

1.2 Second Machine: 16 cores (32 threads)

1.2.1 About OS and CPU

```
$ neofetch --stdout

OS: Manjaro Linux x86_64
Host: MS-7B86 5.0
Kernel: 6.6.52-1-MANJARO
Uptime: 1 min
Packages: 1520 (pacman)
Shell: bash 5.2.32
Resolution: 1920x1080
Terminal: /dev/pts/0
CPU: AMD Ryzen 9 5950X (32) @ 3.400GHz
GPU: NVIDIA GeForce GT 730
Memory: 516MiB / 32016MiB
```

1.2.2 About LAMMPS

```
$ spack -V
0.22.0.dev0 (2b51980904933f8275e9a60f164a0bc6b2eda070)
```

```
$ lmp -h
```

```
Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel
Simulator - 21 Nov 2023
```

<...>

```
Compiler: Clang C++ AMD Clang 16.0.3 (CLANG:
AOCC_4.1.0-Build#270 2023_07_10) with OpenMP 5.0
C++ standard: C++11
MPI v3.1: Open MPI v5.0.1, package: Open MPI
Distribution, ident: 5.0.1, repo rev: v5.0.1,
Dec 20, 2023
```

```
Accelerator configuration:
```

```
OPENMP package API: OpenMP
```

```
OPENMP package precision: double
INTEL package API: OpenMP
INTEL package precision: single mixed double
```

Active compile time flags:

```
-DLAMMPS_GZIP
-DFFT_SINGLE
-DLAMMPS_SMALLBIG
sizeof(smallint): 32-bit
sizeof(imageint): 32-bit
sizeof(tagint): 32-bit
sizeof(bigint): 64-bit
```

<...>

Installed packages:

```
FEP INTEL KSPACE LEPTON MANYBODY MOLECULE
OPENMP OPT RIGID
```

<...>

2 Descriptions of included files

toHDF.py – Simple Python script to convert the particle trajectories into MultiIndex DataFrames and save them in HDF format for further processing. This script can be called from the LAMMPS input script immediately after the main simulation. This is a new vectorized version of the script that is substantially faster. This script can be executed in the folder containing the LAMMPS dump file as:

```
1 python toHDF.py 2e-13 50000000 20000
```

where $2 \cdot 10^{-13}$ is the integration time step in seconds, 50000000 the total number of integration steps in simulation, and 20000 is the dump interval (in time steps).

2.1 MD Trajectories

The **DB.csv** file contains the simulation database. The table contents are shown in Fig. 1.

The subfolders in the **MDtrajectories** directory contain independent simulations with the parameters specified in the database file **DB.csv**. Each folder contains the following four files.

	N	Te	sigma0	w0	l	P0	duration	dt	steps	folder name
0	100	1.0	30	31.0	16	300.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num001_I16_N100_P300.0kW
1	100	1.0	30	31.0	16	100.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num002_I16_N100_P100.0kW
2	100	1.0	30	31.0	16	50.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num003_I16_N100_P50.0kW
3	100	1.0	30	31.0	16	20.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num004_I16_N100_P20.0kW
4	100	1.0	30	31.0	16	10.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num005_I16_N100_P10.0kW
...
392	300	1.0	30	31.0	16	0.1	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num393_I16_N300_P0.1kW
393	300	1.0	30	31.0	16	0.1	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num394_I16_N300_P0.1kW
394	300	1.0	30	31.0	16	2.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num395_I16_N300_P2.0kW
395	300	1.0	30	31.0	16	2.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num396_I16_N300_P2.0kW
396	300	1.0	30	31.0	16	2.0	10.0	2.000000e-13	50000000	sim_num397_I16_N300_P2.0kW

Figure 1: **DB.csv** file content. Here, **N** = $N_i = N_e$ is the number of particles in the simulation, **Te** is the initial temperature of the electrons, **sigma0** is the initial plasma size in μm , **w0** is the laser beam waist in μm , **l** is the Laguerre-Gaussian (LG) beam order, **P0** is the LG beam power in kW, **duration** is the simulation duration in μs , **dt** is the step size of the simulation in seconds, **steps** is the number of integration steps, **folder name** is the name of the subfolder containing the corresponding files.

input.lammps – LAMMPS input script. The main idea of this script is to create a frozen dummy particle at the origin of the simulation. The pairwise interaction between this particle and the electrons/ions reproduces the traps ponderomotive potential. In the case of spherical symmetry, this approach, together with the table potential function, substantially improves computational efficiency.

log.lammps – The LAMMPS output log. This file is used to extract information about the total energy conservation of the simulation.

bound_frac.pkl – Precalculated bound-state fraction at each time step. The following code imports the precomputed *.pkl* file.

```

1 import hickle as hkl
2 time, bounded_electrons_id_list, bounded_ions_id_list,
  ↪ bound_el_num_list, bound_ion_num_list =
  ↪ hkl.load('./bound_frac.pkl')
```

out.hdf – MD trajectories saved as a MultiIndex DataFrame in a compressed HDF file. The following example shows how to open and read this DataFrame.

```

1 import pandas as pd
```

```
2 df = pd.read_hdf ('./MDtrajectories/sim_num022_l16_N500_P20.0kW/out.hdf')
```

It is also necessary to drop the frozen dummy particle with id 3.

```
1 df.drop(3, level=2, axis=0, inplace=True)
```

time	step	id	type	x	y	z	vx	vy	vz	r	v
0.00000	0	1	ion	1.000000e-06	1.867240e-134	-4.437980e-134	-6.322810e-02	-2.855760e-01	1.444220e+00	1.000000e-06	1.473541e+00
		2	electron	1.000000e-05	1.000000e-06	-6.768690e-96	-3.211140e+03	-2.321770e+03	-5.729750e+03	1.004988e-05	6.966496e+03
		3	electron	-1.721770e-54	2.416890e-55	-2.234230e-54	-1.218200e-35	-4.029030e-36	-1.643010e-35	2.831023e-54	2.084664e-35
		4	ion	3.198960e-05	-5.249370e-05	1.413250e-05	6.028410e-01	1.598200e+00	-3.601160e-01	6.307655e-05	1.745664e+00
		5	electron	-1.041830e-06	-5.185770e-06	-4.353120e-06	6.437040e+03	2.857650e+03	5.575460e+03	6.850348e-06	8.982617e+03
...	
0.00001	4998000	599	electron	-1.836470e-06	1.669100e-05	-2.951320e-05	-9.198760e+03	3.137190e+04	1.649650e+03	3.395572e-05	3.273430e+04
		600	ion	-1.025770e-03	-9.681110e-04	-1.226370e-03	-1.190320e+02	-1.130880e+02	-1.425970e+02	1.869071e-03	2.174659e+02
		601	electron	-1.068080e-01	1.414660e-02	-1.360440e-01	-1.110660e+04	1.470580e+03	-1.414600e+04	1.735398e-01	1.804518e+04
		602	ion	-3.411070e-06	-2.942730e-05	-1.513500e-05	1.734850e+01	-2.869350e+01	-2.294960e+01	3.326664e-05	4.063215e+01
		603	electron	-6.791640e-02	1.983790e-02	1.703000e-01	-7.158640e+03	2.086710e+03	1.794780e+04	1.844133e-01	1.943512e+04

1507500 rows x 8 columns

Figure 2: MultiIndex DataFrame containing MD trajectories. All quantities are in SI units.

A MultiIndex DataFrame enables reasonably fast analysis with a table of over 2 million rows. This dump-step spacing is crucial for bound-state fraction calculations. To reduce the size of the dataset, unused per-particle force columns \mathbf{f}_x , \mathbf{f}_y , \mathbf{f}_z from the initial LAMMPS dump are removed and initial DataFrames are compressed with *zlib*.

After reading the HDF file, the desired data can be selected as follows:

```
1 electrons_in_trap = df.loc[:, :, :, 'electron'] ['r'] [df ['r'] < 88e-6].dropna()
```

Here we select particle type 'electron', then select the position-vector magnitude column \mathbf{r} and filter this column for $r < 88 \mu\text{m}$, then drop all *NaN* values. Store the unique time values in a separate variable:

```
1 time = electrons_in_trap.index.get_level_values(0).unique()
```

Then we can calculate the number of electrons remaining in the ponderomotive trap volume at each time step:

```
1 number_of_electrons = []
2 for t in time:
3     number_of_electrons.append(len(electrons_in_trap.loc[t, :, :]))
4
5 #plot time vs number of electrons
6 plt.plot(time*1e6, number_of_electrons)
7 plt.xlabel(r'Time, $\mu\text{s}$')
8 plt.ylabel('Number of electrons in PT')
```

and plot the resulting dependence (blue curve in Fig. 3). Next, we subtract the number of bound electrons from the total number of electrons in the trap.

Figure 3: The number of electrons in the ponderomotive trap volume. The blue curve is the total number of electrons in the trap (electrons with $r < 88 \mu\text{m}$) vs. time. The green curve is the number of bounded electrons (Rydberg states) in the trap. The number of trapped electrons equals the number of trapped ions. The orange curve is the number of free electrons in the trap.

At low initial electron temperatures, three-body recombination leads to the formation of classical bound states (Rydberg states). It is necessary to subtract the number of bounded electrons from the total number of electrons in the trap to isolate the ultracold-plasma (free-electron) component. The complete code used to plot figure 3 is listed below.

```

1     import pandas as pd
2     import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3     import hickle as hkl
4     import numpy as np
5
6     df = pd.read_hdf
7     ↪ ('./MDtrajectories/sim_num022_116_N500_P20.0kW/out.hdf')
8     # drop dummy particle
9     df.drop(3, level=2, axis=0, inplace=True)
10    # read IDs of bounded electrons from precalculated
11    ↪ pkl-file
12    _,bounded_electrons_id_list,_,_,_ = hkl.load
13    ↪ ('./MDtrajectories/sim_num022_116_N500_P20.0kW/bound_frac.pkl')

```

```

11     # Select electrons inside trap volume r < 88um
12     electrons_in_trap =
13     ↪ df.loc[:, :, :, 'electron']['r'][df['r'] < 88e-6].dropna()
14     # Get time column, only unique values
15     time =
16     ↪ electrons_in_trap.index.get_level_values(0).unique()
17     # There is no information about bounded fraction in first
18     ↪ time interval
19     # get this first time interval
20     n = len(time) - len(bounded_electrons_id_list)
21     # select only time steps from n to the end.
22     electrons_in_trap = electrons_in_trap.loc[time[n:], :, :, :]
23     # Get new time column
24     time =
25     ↪ electrons_in_trap.index.get_level_values(0).unique()
26
27     # find number of all electrons and number of bounded
28     ↪ electrons in trap volume
29     number_of_electrons, bounded_fraction = [], []
30     for i in range(len(time)):
31
32         ↪ number_of_electrons.append(len(electrons_in_trap.loc[time[i], :, :, :]))
33         # select only bounded electrons
34         bounded_el_df =
35         ↪ df.loc[time[i], :, bounded_electrons_id_list[i], 'electron']
36         # select bounded particles in PTrap with r < 88um
37         banded_in_PTrap_df =
38         ↪ bounded_el_df[bounded_el_df['r'] < 88e-6]['r'].dropna()
39         # number of bounded particles in PTrap
40         f_B = len(banded_in_PTrap_df)
41         bounded_fraction.append(f_B)
42     # get number of free (plasma) electrons
43     free_electrons = np.array(number_of_electrons) -
44     ↪ np.array(bounded_fraction)
45     # plot the result
46     plt.figure(figsize=(4, 3))
47     plt.plot(time*1e6, number_of_electrons, label = "All
48     ↪ electrons = free + bounded")
49     plt.plot(time*1e6, free_electrons, label = "Free
50     ↪ electrons")
51     plt.plot(time*1e6, bounded_fraction, label = "Bounded
52     ↪ electrons")
53     plt.xlabel(r'Time,  $\mu\text{s}$ ')
54     plt.ylabel('Number of electrons in PT')

```

```

43
44     plt.ylim(0,430)
45     plt.legend()
46     plt.show()

```

2.2 Bound State Fraction

The **Recombination** folder contains scripts for precalculating bound-state fractions. The output of the **pkl_recombination_id_precalc_fast.py** script is the file **bound_frac.pkl**. The script can be executed as follows:

```

1     python pkl_recombination_id_precalc_fast.py
      ↪ ./sim_num009_l16_N200_P50.0kW --mode memory --nproc 2
      ↪ --drop-id 3

```

The first argument **./sim_num009_l16_N200_P50.0kW** is the folder path containing the **out.hdf** file, two **--mode** options useful for large files or limited RAM: **memory** and **reopen**, number of physical CPU cores **--nproc** for parallelization, and dummy particle ID **--drop-id**. In this version of the script, computational performance is optimized. The script **recombination_fast.py** is called from **pkl_recombination_id_precalc_fast.py** and contains the main calculation logic.

The simple Bash script **recombination_pkl_calc.sh** is used to precalculate **bound_frac.pkl** files for all subfolders of some folder specified within the script. This script also determines the number of available physical CPU cores.

The **out_hdf_free_calc.sh** script iterates over the subfolders in a specified directory and precomputes the **out_free.hdf** file by running **out_hdf_free.py** Python script. The **out_free.hdf** contains only the trajectories of free particles (bound particles excluded) which is useful for analysis purposes.

It is possible to plot trajectories (e.g. the absolute value of the radius vector) of bounded particles by their IDs. In figure 4 we plot only 10% of the bound particles to get a clearer representation. We select only particles that are bounded at the end of the simulation (at $t = 10 \mu\text{s}$) and plot their full time evolution.

```

1     import pandas as pd
2     import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3     import hickle as hkl
4     import numpy as np
5
6     df = pd.read_hdf
      ↪ ('./MDtrajectories/sim_num022_l16_N500_P20.0kW/out.hdf')
7     # drop dummy particle
8     df.drop(3, level=2, axis=0, inplace=True)

```

```

9      # read IDs of bounded electrons from precalculated
      ↪ pkl-file
10     _,bounded_electrons_id_list,bounded_ions_id_list,_,_ =
      ↪ hkl.load
      ↪ ('./MDtrajectories/sim_num022_l16_N500_P20.0kW/bound_frac.pkl')
11
12     # Get time column, only unique values
13     time = df.index.get_level_values(0).unique()
14
15     plt.figure(figsize=(7,4))
16     for IDe, IDi in zip(bounded_electrons_id_list[-1][::10],
      ↪ bounded_ions_id_list[-1][::10]):
17         plt.plot(time*1e6, df.loc[:, :, IDe, :] ['r'].values*1e6,
      ↪ '--', color='black')
18         plt.plot(time*1e6, df.loc[:, :, IDi, :] ['r'].values*1e6,
      ↪ color='red', linewidth=0.7)
19     plt.ylim(0,80)
20     plt.xlim(0,10)
21     plt.xlabel(r'Time,  $\mu\text{s}$ ')
22     plt.ylabel(r' $|\vec{r}|, \mu\text{m}$ ')
23     plt.show()

```


Figure 4: The absolute value of the radius vector over time for selected bounded particles in the trap. The red solid lines are ions; the black dashed lines are electrons.

2.3 Energy Conservation

The **EnergyConservation** subfolder contains the IPython notebook with the total energy vs time for each simulation, extracted from the LAMMPS log file. The log-file processing functions are imported into the notebook from the **LammpsLogDataframe.py** file.

2.4 Figures

The **Figures** subfolder contains IPython notebooks and data tables used to create all the figures in the paper.

2.5 Full-Field Simulations

The **RealFieldPTrap/data** folder contains the full-field simulations mentioned in the manuscript. The scripts calculating figures 5 and 6 can be found in the notebook **RealFieldPTrap.ipynb**.

Figure 5: Full-field confinement. Fraction of electrons remaining inside $r < r_0$ for the full-field simulation (black curve) compared with the cycle-averaged trap (blue curves). No measurable loss or heating is observed over 150 ns.

Because resolving the CO_2 optical oscillation requires extremely small time steps, full-field simulations are computationally expensive, and the accessible evolution time is therefore limited to 150 ns. The procedure is as follows: a lithium UNP is first equilibrated for 5 μs in the cycle-averaged ponderomotive potential; the simulation is then continued for 150 ns with the full oscillating CO_2 field, chosen to reproduce the same ponderomotive depth $U_{p0}/k_B = 96$ K with $\ell = 16$ and density $n_0 = 0.24 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. No

measurable heating or particle loss is observed over the full-field evolution, as shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

Figure 6: Electron temperature comparison. Electron temperature evolution for the same simulations as in Fig. 5: full-field simulation (black) and cycle-averaged trap (blue) for $U_{p0}/k_B = 96$ K.

For comparison, using the standard transport estimate $P_{ei} \approx 2\langle U_p \rangle \nu_{ei}$ and the MD-extracted value $\langle U_p \rangle \approx 1.5$ K for this configuration, the expected collisional heating over the full-field simulation window of 150 ns should be on the order of 5 – 20 K. The absence of any measurable increase in T_e therefore indicates that the true optical-frequency IB heating rate is far smaller than this upper-bound estimate.

2.6 Periodic boundary conditions

To explore the frequency dependence more systematically, uniform plasmas in periodic boundaries driven by a spatially uniform AC field from 50 GHz to 30 THz were simulated. The heating agrees with established UNP results in the 50–100 GHz range [19, 47, 48], then drops rapidly with frequency as summarized in Fig. 7. These MD results are consistent with theory: optical-frequency IB heating of low-density UNPs is extremely small [25], and the full-field trap evolution confirms that jitter-induced collisional heating does not limit trap lifetime in this regime.

The **PBCHeatingRates/data** folder contains the full-field simulations mentioned in the manuscript. The scripts that calculate heating rates can be found in the notebook **HeatingRatesDataBase.ipynb**, the script that plots Fig. 7 is **PBC_HeatingRates.py**.

Figure 7: IB heating rate extracted from periodic-box MD simulations with initial electron temperature $T_e = 8$ K, $n_{e,i} = 0.5 \times 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$, $N_{e,i} = 500$, shown for two values of the quiver-to-thermal velocity ratio $p = v_q/v_{th}$. Heating agrees with established UNP results in the 50-100 GHz range [19,47], then drops rapidly with frequency. At CO₂-laser frequency, the heating is below the numerical detection threshold.